

plants) and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea single crop and intercrops were the same.

Single crop rice was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in 15-cm rows. Intercropped rice, seeded at 75 kg seed/ha, had 60-cm row spacing.

Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg N, 13 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha.

All P and K and 25% N were applied basally. The remaining N was applied to rice 50% at 20 d and 25% at 40 d after seeding.

Grain yields were 1.8 t/ha for single

crop rice and 1.4 t/ha for intercropped rice (see table). Mean pigeonpea yield was 1.9 t/ha for single crop and 1.2 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.5, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

A rice - grain legume cropping system for South Coastal Orissa, India

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We studied yields of five rice - grain legume cropping systems with varying fertilizer levels. The dry season crops were green gram *Vigna radiata*, black gram *Vigna mungo*, cowpea *Vigna*

unguiculata, peanut *Arachis hypogaea*, and wheat *Triticum aestivum*. No crop (fallow) was maintained for one treatment to study the nutrient uptake of wet season rice.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.63, 0.25% organic C, 95 kg available P (Bray)/ha, and 375 kg exchangeable K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications, with crops in the main plots and N levels in the subplots. Rice variety Pratap was transplanted on 10 Aug 1986 at 20- × 10-cm spacing with 40-60 kg

PK/ha applied as basal. N was applied in 2 splits at 0, 30, 60, and 90 kg/ha. Harvest was on 19 Nov 1986.

Dry season crops were sown 26 Dec 1986. Grain legumes and peanut received 20-40-0 and wheat 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K was basal, the remaining N was topdressed 20 d after sowing. Preflowering and postflowering irrigations facilitated growth.

Rice - peanut and rice - black gram had the highest total grain yields, closely followed by rice - wheat (Table 1).

Total rice grain yield increased with N, but there was no significant difference between 60 kg N/ha and 90 kg N/ha.

Soil organic C percentage increased with the cropping patterns (Table 2). Available P and exchangeable K decreased in rice - black gram (which had the highest total grain production). □

Table 1. Grain yield of wet season rice and succeeding dry season crops. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	Wet season rice grain yield (t/ha)	Dry season crop grain yield (t/ha)	Total grain produced (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Total return (\$/ha)	Total profit (\$/ha)	Cost-benefit ratio
Rice - cowpea (C-152)	3.9	0.68	4.50	676	953	277	1.41
Rice - green gram (Berhampur local)	4.0	0.26	4.23	583	768	185	1.32
Rice - wheat (Sonalika)	4.0	0.61	4.59	722	900	178	1.25
Rice - black gram (T-9)	4.4	0.68	5.07	600	1048	448	1.74
Rice	4.3	—	4.29	478	686	208	1.43
Rice - peanut (Ak 12-24)	4.1	1.07	5.13	820	1244	423	1.52
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	0.32	—	—	—	—
<i>N levels</i>							
No N	3.6	0.52	4.10	—	—	—	—
30 kg N/ha	4.1	0.54	4.63	—	—	—	—
60 kg N/ha	4.2	0.57	4.81	—	—	—	—
90 kg N/ha	4.4	0.56	4.98	—	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	0.1	ns	0.14	—	—	—	—

Table 2. Soil test value after dry season crop. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	pH	Organic C (%)	Available P (kg/ha)	Exchangeable K (kg/ha)
Rice - cowpea	5.57	0.43	125	255
Rice - green gram	5.35	0.31	161	342
Rice - wheat	5.40	0.28	125	242
Rice - black gram	5.65	0.30	137	155
Rice - fallow (no crop)	5.70	0.33	147	227
Rice - peanut	5.60	0.35	125	227
Initial soil test value	5.63	0.25	95	375

Rice-based cropping sequences for northwestern Himalayas uplands

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We compared 7 irrigated upland rice-based intensive cropping sequences with traditional rice - wheat/potato sequences on VPKAS experimental fields (1,250 m). The experiment was conducted 1982-85 in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Three cycles were completed.

Soil was loamy with neutral pH and medium fertility. Recommended

improved cultivars and other cultural practices were followed for the different crops. A minimum 7 d was taken between crops for field preparation.

Highest total yields, net returns, and

benefit:cost ratio were with rice - radish - onion, followed by rice - radish - vegetable pea - french bean. Rice - wheat had the lowest yields and net returns.

Protein, carbohydrates, fats, and energy

yields were highest with rice - radish - vegetable pea - french bean, rice - rapeseed *Brassica campestris* var. *toria* - potato/ cabbage, rice - radish - potato, and rice - radish - onion (see table). □

Production efficiency of rice-based crop sequences under irrigated upland conditions. UPKAS, Uttar Pradesh, India, 1982-85.

Crop sequence ^a	Yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio	Protein (t/ha)	Carbohydrate (t/ha)	Fat (t/ha)	Energy (kcal × 10 ³ /ha)
1. Rice (VL 8)	4.6	514	506	2.0	0.8	0.09	6.7	31,073
Wheat (CPAN 1796)	4.4							
2. Rice (VL 8)	4.7	877	716	1.8	0.7	0.05	9.1	39,364
Potato	23.8							
3. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1061	849	1.8	0.9	0.6	8.6	43,727
Rapeseed	1.5							
Potato	23.4							
4. Rice (VL 8)	4.7	1057	951	1.9	0.9	0.08	10.0	42,964
Radish	22.5							
Potato	23.7							
5. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1286	1086	1.8	1.1	0.07	9.3	42,189
Cabbage	23.5							
Potato	23.5							
6. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	862	664	1.8	0.9	0.6	4.3	26,361
Rapeseed	1.4							
Cabbage	20.9							
7. Rice (VLK39)	3.7	1056	2215	3.1	1.1	0.1	9.8	44,233
Radish	31.3							
Onion (VL 67)	52.3							
8. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	694	613	1.9	0.9	0.1	6.4	30,059
Radish	24.4							
Wheat (Sonalika)	3.7							
9. Rice (VLK39)	3.8	1072	1367	2.3	1.8	0.07	7.0	35,780
Radish	23.2							
Vegetable bean (Arkel)	16.6							
French bean (VL 1)	12.9							

^aPotato variety was Kufri Jyoti; radish, Jap. White Long; cabbage, Golden Acre; rapeseed, T9.

Piara sowing of rabi pulses after rice at South Coastal Orissa, India

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Farmers have difficulty engaging enough bullock and farm power to undertake tillage of rabi pulses because power remains engaged for postharvest processing of rice. Timely seeding of rabi pulses should take advantage of field moisture. We evaluated

broadcasting of rabi pulses in ricefields before or soon after harvest (piara cultivation).

Four rabi pulses, cowpea C-152, green gram Berhampur local, black gram Sarala, and chickpea (local) were sown in a randomized block design with 4 replications during 1987-88 dry season on a plot where rice IR36 was grown during 1987-88 wet season with 60-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Pulse seeds were broadcast into standing rice (M₁) 1 wk before harvest, and in a separate plot soon after harvest (M₂). Soil was sandy loam with 6.1 pH, 0.38% organic C, 16 kg Olsen's P, and 305 kg available K/ ha.

There were no significant differences in yield and yield characters between M₁ and M₂ because there was adequate soil moisture for germination and growth. Cowpea had highest seed yield, closely followed by black gram. Green gram yield was lowest. Chickpea plants remained stunted because of low root growth and they failed to bear any pod. Cowpea was free from disease and pests. Green gram had severe infection of powdery mildew, with less on black gram and chickpea. Leaf beetles affected all pulses at seedling and vegetative growth phases. □